

AN ANALYSIS OF GST IMPACT ON MOTORBIKE INDUSTRY IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Indian bike industry is one of the biggest on the planet to the extent the volume of generation and deals are concerned. Bikes shape a necessary piece of Indian streets. Running from moderateness to energy to style explanation, purposes behind purchasing a bike are numerous for Indian clients. The development in Indian Automobile Industry owed the most to a lofty upsurge saw in the bike fragment in 2015. The volume development recorded in the 2015-16 monetary year remained at an estimable 14.8 percent on a year-on-year premise. The business can possibly develop to wind up a noteworthy financial patron. The Government of India has likewise perceived the significance of Automobile industry holds in the Indian economy and consequently is at present dealing with Automotive Mission Plan 2026 to set focuses for the business for the year 2026. The Government of India has intended to execute of GST to the assembling segment in India. The goal of this investigation is the effect of GST on Automobile and bike parts in India. 'Make in India' crusade of the Government of India is additionally going to pull in more remote venture into Indian bike portion making further development openings in the coming years.

Keywords: GST, Two wheeler Sector, Economic Development and growth

I. Introduction

The vehicle business is one of the key drivers that lift the financial development of the nation. Car part in India is developing quick and the development design appears to have an unmistakable relationship with the changes related strategies those affected both household request design and in addition exchange. The car business is moving at a quick pace whereby expanding the quantity of vehicles on streets which incorporates all the four wheelers, three wheelers and bikes. These vehicles travel either inside the city, while others travel even outside the city all the time. During the evening, one can without much of a stretch call attention to the overwhelming vehicles, extending from auto bearers to oil tankers, holder movers, trucks and transports, all charged by a substantial obligation diesel motor on streets. These vehicles cover long separations at various circumstances with various climate conditions.

The Auto business as of now utilizes more than 30 million individuals both specifically and in a roundabout way. The automobile business is a key work generator in the OEM (Original Equipment Manufacturer) industrial facility that makes the vehicles, in the inbound auto segment and coordinations industry that makes and conveys parts and frameworks and the out bound coordinations and merchant organize that offers, keeps up and disperses the autos. Each vehicle created, produces optional and tertiary business. The business creates work of 13 people for each truck, 6 people for every auto and four people for every three wheeler and one individual for bikes. It is vital to value the part's multiplier impact on monetary movement. On the off chance that the business creates according to its potential, it could produce work of more than 35 million individuals by 2020.

The Automotive Mission Plan for the time of 2006-2016 means to influence India to rise as a worldwide car center point. The thought is to settle on India as the goal decision for plan and fabricate of vehicles and auto parts, with yields taking off to achieve US\$ 145 billion which is fundamentally representing over 10% of the GDP. This would likewise give facilitate work to more than 25 million individuals by 2016 making the vehicle the dawn part of the economy.

II. Indian Bike Industry

The Indian bike industry influenced a little start in the mid 1950's when To car Product of India (API) began fabricating bikes in the nation, until 1958, API and Enfield (cruisers) were the sole makers. The bike advertise was opened to remote rivalry in the mid 1980's, getting the then market pioneers Escorts and Enfield. The section of Indo-Japanese joint wander introduced another time for the Indian bike industry through the 100cc cruisers. Among cruisers, four stroke vehicle represents a noteworthy piece of offers and this isn't astounding since fuel productivity positions the first among all parameters. Aside from these some broad factors in India, for example, moderateness, working spot get to, enormous rates of young people and so on likewise contributed towards the development of this section.

Bikes have assumed an essential part in rising development of Indian car Industry. The Indian bike industry is encountering a noteworthy move in its shape and structure. The bike business is the most lucrative industry and the central point affecting interest for bikes in India are expanding white collar class populace, Easy financing, Festivals and weddings, Weak Public transport, Convenience and simplicity of working. . The bike business is maybe the most happening place as far as new models propelled, updated items and inventive showcasing systems. Today the Indian bike showcases in exceptionally aggressive the various players who offer everything without exception a customer requests and that too at reasonable cost. The Indian bike industry is commanded by six players, Hero, Honda, Bajaj, TVS, Yamaha and

Suzuki, who represent 80 percent of the aggregate bike showcase. Alternate players including Kinetic engines, LML and others represent the rest of the 20 percent of the market.

I. III. GST in India

The GST as the greatest tax assessment change and is essentially a proposed impose change right now. This is aberrant assessment much like the VAT, Service charge, diversion impose, and so forth and this would be collected by the state and focus as State GST and Centre GST on the fabricate, deal and utilization of all merchandise and ventures the whole way across India.

Products and Enterprises Tax is a circuitous duty which was presented in India on 1 July 2017 and was appropriate all through India which supplanted various falling charges imposed by the focal and state governments. It was presented as The Constitution (One Hundred and First Amendment) Act 2017, after the section of Constitution 122nd Amendment Bill. The GST is administered by a GST Council and its Chairman is the Finance Minister of India. Under GST, merchandise and ventures are burdened at the accompanying rates, 0%, 5%, 12%, 18% and 28%. There is a unique rate of 0.25% on harsh valuable and semi-valuable stones and 3% on gold likewise a cess of 15% or different rates over 28% GST applies on couple of things like circulated air through beverages, extravagance autos and tobacco items. GST was at first proposed to supplant a large number of aberrant assessments with a brought together duty and was in this manner set to drastically reshape the nation's 2 trillion dollar economy the rate of GST in India is between twofold to four times that demanded in different nations like Singapore.

India is proposed to have a double GST set up in 2017, which will be the greatest change in the nation's assessment structure in decades. The primary target of consolidating the GST is to wipe out assessment on impose i.e. twofold tax collection which falls from the assembling level to the utilization level. High duty rates and ensuing high costs of vehicles have an unsafe impact of bringing down volumes, bringing down gross expense accumulations and at last bringing down development in the auto segment.

IV. Objectives of the study

1. To Understand the impact of GST on Two wheeler industry in India
2. To Examine the GST rules applicable to select two wheeler companies in India.

V. Methodology of the study

The methodology used for the study is purely secondary in nature. Reports issued by the

Government of India, GST Act Proceedings, and Various committee reports on GST, For this research study, the secondary data were collected from research articles and papers in International and National journals and books, magazines and news articles, websites are being referred for the current study. The secondary data helped to structure the review of literature.

VI. Impact of the GST on Bike Industry

GST impact on bikes will now affect costs of bikes as the Goods and Services Tax (GST) comes into put, as from the 1 July 2017, yet just hardly. GST prompts a more brought together expense structure, so now bike makers will charge a uniform cost crosswise over India. This will bring about ex-showroom costs of bikes getting to be same crosswise over India, with a level 28 for every penny GST. Yet, the GST structure for bikes has been ordered into two gatherings - bikes with motors underneath 350 cc and bikes with motors over 350 cc.

Along these lines, GST impact will have bikes with motor limit underneath 350 cc will draw in a level 28 for every penny, down 2 for every penny from the present 30 for each penny in different charges, including extract obligation, VAT, CST, and so forth. This section incorporates all Royal Enfield 350 bicycles which have genuine motor limit of 346 cc. Be that as it may, bikes over 350 cc motor limit will pull in an extra cess of 3 for every penny, far beyond the 28 for each penny GST.

Prices of two-wheelers before and after GST

ENGINE CAPACITY	EXAMPLES	BEFORE GST	AFTER GST	DIFFERENCE
Below 350 cc	Honda Activa 4G, Hero Splendor, Bajaj Pulsar 150, Royal Enfield Classic 350	30 per cent	28 per cent	- 2 per cent
Above 350 cc	KTM 390 Duke, Harley-Davidson Street Rod, Ducati Scrambler, Triumph Street Twin	30 per cent	28 per cent and additional 3 per cent cess (Total 31 per cent)	+ 1 per cent

GST slabs and impact on two-wheeler prices

Numerous bike makers are as yet endeavoring to make sense of what will be the genuine advantages on costs which can be passed on to clients. Onlookers say the genuine effect of GST on the bike business can't be checked for the time being, in the following month or two. Under GST, crude material expenses will go up, so in the end, the real effect on costs must be discovered over a time of 6-8 months. Different makers have discharged their refreshed costs

after the usage of GST. The discharges recommend a peripheral drop in costs of the mass section bikes which is relied upon to bring about a superior industry development.

Viable from July 1, 2017, the duty on bicycles and bikes up to 350cc has descended and consequently will cost 3-5% less expensive. Be that as it may, motorbikes with 350cc dislodging or more will pull in an extra 3% cess which will bring about the general duty of 31%. you should perceive what is the adjustment in the cost of the bikes or any bike after GST affect.

Since GST has entered the market, top bikes organizations of India have cut costs on their items. The organizations that have reported the value cut are as per the following:

- ❖ Market pioneer Hero Moto Corp has sliced costs by up to 1,800 on its bikes relying upon the model and the state from which it has been acquired.
- ❖ TVS Motor Company has as of late decreased the costs of its models by up to 4,150 contingent upon the state from which the bike has been acquired.
- ❖ Honda Motorcycle and Scooter India (HMSI) has likewise held delivers the cut estimated classification and lessened the costs of its bicycles and bikes by up to 5,500 contingent upon model and state.
- ❖ Suzuki Motorcycle India and Yamaha have additionally lessened costs as a move towards the profiting its clients post GST dispatch.

VIII. Effect of GST on Major Brands

Following the GST rollout, assess on bikes has been fragmented relying upon the motor limit. With the new GST structure actualized crosswise over India from July 1, 2017, there have been changes in the costs of most bikes. Bicycles with motor limits under 350cc get burdened at 28 percent, while those more than 350cc get an extra 3 percent cess, taking their powerful expense to 31 percent. The past total expense structure for bikes was 30.2 percent, which implies littler limit bicycles now get saddled less and there is a peripheral increment for higher limit ones. There have by and large been value cuts in all cases for most mass-advertise cruisers, and we're investigating estimating changes from different makers.

Duty Structure for Two Wheelers (Pre-GST)

Segment	Excise Duty	NCCD	VAT	CST	Effective Tax
Two Wheeler	12.5%	1.0%	12.5%	2.0%	30.2%

Duty Structure for Two Wheelers (Post-GST)

Segment	Before GST	After GST
Two Wheeler (Engine Size <350cc)	30.2%	28.0%
Two Wheeler (Engine Size >350cc)	30.2%	31.0%

Source: GST Documents, ICRA research; * VAT may be higher in some states

VIII.1. Hero Moto Corp

Mr Pawan Munjal, MD and CEO, Hero Moto Corp said that "It is to be sure a noteworthy day – a genuine sign of 'Solidarity in Diversity'. The Goods and Services Tax (GST) mirrors the development and readiness of the Indian equitable framework to work towards the more prominent advantage. Mass market items from India's biggest bike producer have seen decreases running from Rs 400 to about Rs 1,800, on its mass-offering models. The advantages shift from state to state, contingent upon the pre and post GST rates. Also, two or three states, where the prior duty was much lower, will see negligible increments for a couple of models. A portion of the organization's more premium fragment offerings will see a diminishment of up to Rs 4,000, contingent upon the area.

Hero Bike Prices after GST

Model Name	Pre-GST Price	Post GST Price	Savings
Hero Splendor Plus	Rs 51823	Rs 51,323	Rs 500
Hero Glamour 125	Rs 63,578	62,978	Rs 600
Her Passion Pro i3S	Rs 58849	57,849	Rs 990
Hero HF Deluxe	RS 45,975	45,575	Rs 400
Hero Xtreme 200 S	Rs 91200	90,000	Rs 1200

VIII.2. Bajaj

Bajaj has passed the GST benefits to its customers and the brand has reduced the price of all motorcycles except Dominar 400 because Dominar is powered by a 373cc engine. According to GST, the bikes which are under 350cc will now attract a tax rate of 28 percent instead of 30 percent under the old tax structure.

Bajaj Bike Prices after GST

Model Name	Pre-GST Price	Post GST Price	Savings
Bajaj Pulsar NS200	Rs 97600	Rs 96700	Rs 900
Pulsar 220F	Rs 92200	Rs 91,500	Rs 700
Pulsar RS200	Rs 1,22800	Rs 1,21800	Rs 1000

VIII.3. HONDA:

Honda Motorcycles & Scooters India has passed the GST benefits to its customers and the brand has reduced the price of all motorcycles and scooters except their superbikes because all of them are powered by a 650cc or 1000cc engine. According to GST, the bikes and scooters which are under 350cc, will attract a tax rate of 28 percent instead of 30 percent under the old tax structure. GST tax on bikes above 350cc is 31 percent (increased from 30 percent).

Honda Bike Prices after GST

Model Name	Pre-GST Price	Post GST Price	Savings
Honda CB Hornet 160R	Rs 82,600	Rs 81,800	Rs 800
Honda Activa 4G	Rs 51,200	Rs 50,800	Rs 400
Honda Navi 110	Rs 41,600	Rs 41,200	Rs 400
Honda CLIQ(New)	Rs 42,500	Rs 42,500	Rs 0
CB Unicorn 160	Rs 75,000	Rs74,600	Rs 400

VIII.4.TVS:

TVS has announced similar benefits as Hero MotoCorp, with their commuter segment models getting a reduction in the range of Rs 350 to Rs 1,500, depending on the state. The company's premium motorcycles such as the Apache RTR 200 have become cheaper by around Rs 4,150, subject to the location of purchase.

TVS Bike Prices after GST

Model Name	Pre-GST Price	Post GST Price	Savings
TVS Apache RTR 200	Rs 93315	Rs 92315	Rs 1000
TVS Jupiter	Rs 49966	Rs 49766	Rs 200
TVS Apache RTR 180	Rs 91757	Rs 91357	Rs 400
TVS Apache RTR 160	Rs 79304	Rs 78904	Rs 1000
TVS Star city Plus	Rs 46,530	Rs 45,390	Rs 1100

VIII.5. Yamaha:

Nearly all of Yamaha's models on offer in the country fall in the 28 percent GST bracket and have seen price changes. The company has been extremely proactive about its post-GST pricing and the website now reflects the new prices for all their models in all states.

Yamaha Bike Prices after GST

Model	Pre-GST price	Post-GST price	Savings
YZF-R15 v2.0	Rs 1,19,788	Rs 1,18,838	950
FZ-S FI	Rs 83,674	Rs 83,042	632
FZ FI	Rs 81,611	Rs 81,040	571
FZ25	Rs 1,20,385	Rs 1,19,335	1050
Fascino	Rs 55,015	Rs 54,593	422

VIII.6. Suzuki:

Suzuki Motorcycle India Private Limited (SMIPL), a subsidiary of one of the world’s leading two-wheeler manufacturers, Suzuki Motor Corporation, Japan welcomes the revolutionary new GST tax reform and has decided to pass on the benefits of the reform to its customers. Suzuki vehicles which fall under the 28% tax slab will see a reduction in price. The company products will now be accessible to more Indians.

Suzuki Bike Prices after GST

Model Name	Pre-GST Price	Post GST Price	Savings
Suzuki Gixxer SF FI	Rs 93,900	Rs 93,000	Rs 900
Gixxer SF	Rs 90,100	Rs 89,200	Rs 900
Let’s	Rs 48,700	Rs 48,200	Rs 500
Access Disc	Rs 58,000	Rs 57,500	Rs 500
Hayate EP	Rs 53,000	Rs 52,400	Rs 600

IX. CONCLUSION

After GST, Bajaj Auto, Hero, Yamaha, TVS, Suzuki, it is currently Honda bikes that has chosen to stretch out the GST advantages to its clients. Every one of the bikes having motor dislodging of under 350cc will turn into somewhat less expensive beginning first July, 2017. The reason being, these will now draw in duties of 28 percent as against 30 percent in the old structure. American bike maker Indian Motorcycle has announced a reduction in prices of its motorcycles by up to 12 percent following GST. The Indian Scout is cheaper by Rs 1.76 lakh to Rs 12.99 lakh. The Indian Dark Horse sees a price reduction of Rs 2.15 lakh and now costs Rs 21.25 lakh. Price for the Indian Classic Chief has reduced by Rs 2.21 lakh and it now costs Rs 21.99 lakh. Then again, bikes having motor limit of more than 350cc will see a climb in cost in that capacity vehicles will pull in an extra cess of 3 percent, which will take the general GST to 31 percent. Effect of duty falling will likewise leave that will lessen general cost of vehicle fabricating as all duties on input paid will be counterbalanced with the yield risk of GST.

X. REFERENCES

- ❖ P. chaurasia, S. Singh, P. Kumar Sen of Goods and Service Tax in the growth of Indian economy”, “ International technology and management February 2016.
- ❖ <http://www.economictimes.com>
- ❖ <http://www.gstindia.com>
- ❖ <http://economictimes.indiatimes.com>
- ❖ [http:// www.taxguru.in](http://www.taxguru.in)
- ❖ <http://www.cbec.gov.in/htdocs-cbec/gst>
- ❖ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Goods_and_Services_Tax_\(India\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Goods_and_Services_Tax_(India))
- ❖ [http://www.siamindia.com/publications.](http://www.siamindia.com/publications)